

Supplementary Material

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Designing Interpretable Deep Learning Applications for Functional Genomics: a Quantitative Analysis

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1 Supplementary Methods

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1.1 Literature retrieval

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During literature identification, we followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines [cite]. We searched five different databases up to April 2023: Medline, Embase, Web of Science Core Collection, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, and Google Scholar (200 top-ranked). The search strategy was developed in cooperation with the Erasmus MC Medical Library and combined terms describing deep learning architectures (e.g. "neural network", "deep learning"), data types (e.g. "genomics", "transcriptomics"), and network interpretation (e.g. "explainable", "interpretable"). The lack of independent reviewers prevented a fully unbiased literature search; however good reporting guidelines were adhered to, resulting in a narrative review with systematic base. The exact search strings constructed for each database are:

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1.1.1 Search strings: Medline

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(exp Neural Networks, Computer/ OR Multifactor Dimensionality Reduction/ OR (autoencoder* OR auto-encoder* OR ((neural) ADJ3 (network*)) OR ((deep) ADJ3 (learning*)) OR latent-space* OR perceptron*).ab,ti,kf.) AND (Genomics/ OR Metabolomics/ OR exp Proteomics/ OR Epigenomics/ OR Genome/ OR Metabolome/ OR Proteome/ OR Transcriptome/ OR MicroRNAs/ OR Epistasis, Genetic/ OR Genetics, Population/ OR (omics OR genomic* OR metabolomic* OR proteomic* OR multiomic* OR multi-omic* OR transcriptomic* OR methylomic* OR epigenomic* OR epigenetic* OR metagenomic* OR genome* OR metabolome* OR proteome* OR transcriptom* OR microRNA* OR micro-RNA* OR miRNA* OR mi-RNA* OR epistasis OR epistatic* OR ((population*) ADJ3 (genetics*))).ab,ti,kf.) AND (Data Interpretation, Statistical/ OR Data Visualization/ OR (interpretabilit* OR explainabilit* OR interpretabl* OR explainabl* OR visualization* OR visualisation* OR ((meaningful*) ADJ3 (explain* OR explain*)) OR ((biologic*) ADJ3 (informed)) OR ((black) ADJ3 (box))).ab,ti,kf. OR (interpret* OR explain* OR visual* OR visib*).ti.) AND english.la.

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1.1.2 Search strings: Embase

('artificial neural network'/exp OR 'deep learning'/de OR 'dimensionality reduction'/de
OR 'nonlinear dimensionality reduction'/de OR 'deep neural network'/de OR 'multi-
layer perceptron'/de OR (autoencoder* OR auto-encoder* OR ((neural) NEAR/3 (net-
work*)) OR ((deep) NEAR/3 (learning*)) OR latent-space* OR perceptron*):ab,ti,kw)
AND ('omics'/de OR 'genomics'/exp OR 'metabolomics'/exp OR 'proteomics'/exp OR
'multiomics'/de OR 'transcriptomics'/exp OR 'epigenetics'/exp OR 'genome'/de OR
'metabolome'/de OR 'proteome'/de OR 'transcriptome'/de OR 'microRNA'/exp OR
'epistasis'/de OR 'population genetics'/de OR (omics OR genomic* OR metabolomic*
OR proteomic* OR multiomic* OR multi-omic* OR transcriptomic* OR methylomic*
OR epigenomic* OR epigenetic* OR metagenomic* OR genome* OR metabolome* OR
proteome* OR transcriptom* OR microRNA* OR micro-RNA* OR miRNA* OR mi-
RNA* OR epistasis OR epistatic* OR ((population*) NEAR/3 (genetics*)):ab,ti,kw)
AND ('interpretability'/de OR 'interpretation'/de OR 'visualization'/de OR 'black box
warning'/de OR 'data visualization'/de OR (interpretabilit* OR explainabilit* OR in-
terpretabl* OR explainabl* OR visualization* OR visualisation* OR ((meaningful*)
NEAR/3 (explan* OR explain*)) OR ((biologic*) NEAR/3 (informed)) OR ((black)
NEAR/3 (box))):ab,ti,kw OR (interpret* OR explain* OR visual* OR visib*):ti) AND
[ENGLISH]/lim

1.1.3 Search strings: Cochrane

((autoencoder* OR auto-encoder* OR ((neural) NEAR/3 (network*)) OR ((deep) NEAR/3
(learning*)) OR latent-space* OR perceptron*):ab,ti) AND ((omics OR genomic* OR
metabolomic* OR proteomic* OR multiomic* OR multi-omic* OR transcriptomic*
OR methylomic* OR epigenomic* OR epigenetic* OR metagenomic* OR genome* OR
metabolome* OR proteome* OR transcriptom* OR microRNA* OR micro-RNA* OR
miRNA* OR mi-RNA* OR epistasis OR epistatic* OR ((population*) NEAR/3 (genet-
ics*)):ab,ti) AND ((interpretabilit* OR explainabilit* OR interpretabl* OR explain-
abl* OR visualization* OR visualisation* OR ((meaningful*) NEAR/3 (explan* OR
explain*)) OR ((biologic*) NEAR/3 (informed)) OR ((black) NEAR/3 (box))):ab,ti
OR (interpret* OR explain* OR visual* OR visib*):ti)

1.1.4 Search strings: Web of Science

TS=(autoencoder* OR auto-encoder* OR ((neural) NEAR/2 (network*)) OR ((deep) NEAR/2 (learning*)) OR latent-space* OR perceptron*) AND TS=(omics OR genomic* OR metabolomic* OR proteomic* OR multiomic* OR multi-omic* OR transcriptomic* OR methylomic* OR epigenomic* OR epigenetic* OR metagenomic* OR genome* OR metabolome* OR proteome* OR transcriptom* OR microRNA* OR microRNA* OR miRNA* OR mi-RNA* OR epistasis OR epistatic* OR ((population*) NEAR/2 (genetics*)) AND (TS=(interpretabilit* OR explainabilit* OR interpretabl* OR explainabl* OR visualization* OR visualisation* OR ((meaningful*) NEAR/2 (explain* OR explain*)) OR ((biologic*) NEAR/2 (informed)) OR ((black) NEAR/2 (box))) OR TI=(interpret* OR explain* OR visual* OR visib*)) AND LA=(English)

1.2 Taxonomy

In order to better classify the numerous interpretation strategies deployed, we adopted the taxonomy defined by Zhang et al. which utilises three dimensions to categorise interpretation approaches [1]. The first dimension divides the existing approaches into *active* and *passive* according to whether they require to change the network architecture or can be applied post-hoc. The second dimension describes the type of explanations, differentiating between four major types: *logic rules*, *hidden semantics*, *attributions* and *explanations by examples* (ordered by decreasing explanatory power). The possibility of extracting logic rules provides the most powerful, clear, and explicit explanations, while providing examples which may be similar to the test case requires further human interpretation to be informative. The most common category of methods, *attributions*, assign credits to input features, enabling the possibility to rank them according to their influence on the final output. In case not the final output is of interest but preceding layers, attribution methods can be applied to hidden neurons instead; these methods are categorised as *hidden semantics*. The third and last dimension describes the level of interpretability with regard to the input space, differentiating between global, semi-local, and local approaches. Global interpretability refers to understanding the overall decision logic of a model and its behaviour across all regions of the feature space, i.e. a whole population. Local explanations, however, only describes a small area of the

feature space near a point of interest, for example a patient [2]. As the transition 101
between global and local interpretation is soft, Zhang et al. additionally include the 102
category of semi-local approaches which can be thought of as e.g. a group of similar 103
patients. 104

By combining these three dimensions, interpretation approaches can be efficiently grouped 105
together, gaining a good overview of trends in the field. However, as the landscape of 106
algorithms to implement each of these three dimensions is very broad, we additionally 107
extracted details regarding the interpretation strategy (*Interpretation strategy*), in case 108
of attribution approaches the interpretation algorithm (*post-hoc interpretation method*), 109
as well as the source of prior knowledge if active networks utilising biological knowledge 110
were designed (*prior knowledge*). 111

2 Supplementary Figures 112

Supplementary Figure 1: **Input sizes of the neural networks.** The inputsize used in each study for the neural network coloured per data type

Supplementary Figure 2: **Levels of interpretation.** The level of interest for the interpretations of the deep learning model. Most studies focused on extracting gene and pathway level information from the neural networks. The category *other* includes: custom (5.7%), cell type (2.8%), tissue type (1.1%), miRNA (1.1%), protein (1.1%), cell type (1.1%), and CpG site (1.1%) annotations

References

- [1] Y. Zhang, P. Tino, A. Leonardis, and K. Tang, "A Survey on Neural Network Interpretability," vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 726–742.
- [2] D. S. Watson, *Interpretable Machine Learning for Genomics*. Human Genetics, Springer.

Supplementary Figure 3: Sources of prior knowledge used in active interpretation strategies.

Supplementary Figure 4: UpSet plot with the data types and the combinations of data types found in this study, data types are colored per main category. The general occurrence of the data type can be found in the horizontal bar graph while the standing bars provide information on the combinations of data types